

Land Degradation Neutrality through Carbon Farming Practices

Govindaraj Kamalam Dinesh

SRM College of Agricultural Sciences, SRM Institute of Science and Technology,
Baburayanpettai – 603 201, Chengalpattu, Tamil Nadu, India

gkdineshiari@gmail.com

Land is a non-renewable resource, and some detrimental consequences of deteriorating processes on land quality, such as a decrease in effective rooting depth, are irreversible. Land degradation is a significant worldwide problem, since more than 70% of the Earth's ice-free land has already been affected by human activity. Desertification occurs on around 33% of the Earth's geographical area and impacts over one billion people, with half of them residing in Africa.

Land degradation negatively impacts the ability of soil to support the variety of living organisms, plant growth and the well-being of ecosystems. The decrease in land quality due to land degradation has an influence on soil productivity. Soil erosion and desertification have caused a 50% decrease in the production of some farms. However, the utilisation of extra inputs and the adoption of superior technologies may readily disguise the land degradation on production.

The annual worldwide cost of land degradation, specifically in relation to agriculture, amounts to around US\$ 500 billion. In response to the alarming ecological and economic situations, the United Nations General Assembly approved the "Sustainable Development Goals" in 2015. These goals include a specific objective to address desertification and rehabilitate land that has been damaged. The objective is to

achieve land degradation neutrality by 2030. The framework followed was to minimise > mitigate > counteract the land degradation.

Attaining land degradation neutrality (LDN), which refers to maintaining or enhancing the quality of soil and land resources from degradation. It is crucial for achieving the food security and climate resilience. To achieve the LDN, the carbon farming is a potentially effective method in the agroecosystems. Carbon farming offers a comprehensive approach to address land degradation and promote a sustainable, carbon-neutral future. Carbon farming practices using sustainable land management strategies to enhance carbon sequestration and climate resilience in soil and vegetation. Some important techniques include:

Agroforestry

Reforestation and afforestation have the potential to greatly improve carbon sequestration on areas that have been already degraded. The majority of commonly used agroforestry (AF) systems are often sustainable or resilient, although they often encounter issues such as conservation of natural resources, productivity, land degradation, unpredictable climate, desertification and ecological concerns. The use of carbon farming techniques (integrated farming, organic farming, natural farming, permaculture, regenerative farming, precision farming) coupled with agroforestry climate plays a crucial role in enhancing livelihood diversification, improving food security, promoting conservation and effective use of natural resources, delivering a range of ecosystem services, and alleviating pressure on soil. China and India have fronted international initiatives to enhance sustainable land use, resulting in a 5% expansion in global green space since 2000.

Cover cropping and crop rotation

Methods such as implementing cover cropping, and incorporating crop residues into the soil will improve both soil fertility and carbon sequestration. The improvement in organic carbon will minimise the erosion in soil. Legumes (e.g., clover, vetch, peas), grasses (e.g., rye, oats, barley), brassicas (e.g., radish, mustard) can be used as a cover crop to conserve the soil fertility and erosion losses. The crop residues such as corn, wheat straw, soybean, rice straw and pulses stalks can be used as a residues for soil cover to conserve the soil moisture, avoid erosion, and improve the soil organic carbon after certain period of time.

Organic Farming and Natural Farming

Organic farming and natural farming include simple techniques such as application of well decomposed organic manures, throwing of seedballs during monsoons, permanent soil cover with previous crop residues, natural method of pest and disease control, avoidance of chemicals application, minimising the tillage. These techniques will improves the soil organic carbon and it enhances the soil biodiversity by which it

improves the soil health and fertility to tackle the soil from degradation and desertification.

Regenerative and zero tillage farming

The minimal or no soil disturbance, permanent soil cover, diverse crop rotations, efficient nutrient management are the core principles in conservation agriculture which directly enhances the soil organic carbon and conserve the natural resources from depletion. It indirectly helps to improve the soil biota such as earthworm, collembola, and microbial diversity. Minimising the soil disturbance, permanent living root growth, soil cover, integrating livestock, and maximizing the crop diversity are the five core principles of regenerative agriculture which helps to Regenerative agriculture helps achieve land degradation neutrality (LDN) through the following ways: enhancing soil health by improving the soil structure and fertility, reducing soil erosion, promoting biodiversity for ecosystem resilience, reduced chemical inputs through which minimizing soil contamination and encouraging natural pest control.

Sustainable Grazing

Ecological grazing refers to a method of grazing livestock that takes into account the ecological impact on the environment. Implementing sustainable livestock management strategies, such as rotational grazing, has the potential to enhance plant cover and promote the storage of carbon in the soil. The use of trees into grazing and agricultural systems may improve productivity, biodiversity, and carbon sequestration.

About the Author

Dr. G K Dinesh is an Assistant Professor of Environmental Sciences at SRM College of Agricultural Sciences, SRM Institute of Science and Technology, Acharapakkam Campus, Chengalpattu, India. He completed his PhD in Environmental Science from ICAR-Indian Agricultural Research Institute, New Delhi, by securing National level 5th rank and awarded with IARI Ph.D. Senior Research Fellowship in the national level entrance examination. He is also a recipient of the 'Young advantage fellow' by Institute of Bioecosciences, USA and Research Fellow (invited honorary position) by INTI International University, Malaysia. He completed his Bachelors in Agriculture from Annamalai University, Chidambaram, Tamil Nadu, INDIA, and obtained his Masters' in (Agriculture) Environmental Science from Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, INDIA and awarded fellowship for his excellence in studies with Student Junior Research Fellowship from TNAU-Private Industrial Agency Scheme (Sakthi Sugars Pvt. Ltd.) and worked on a long-term impact assessment study on distillery effluent application on soil and Cassava and Jasmine crops. Furthermore, he did a Master's thesis on the Ecology of birds and insects in organic and inorganic paddy ecosystem. He Qualified ICAR and UGC National Eligibility test for Professorship for several times. His PhD research work in the area of Conservation agriculture and ecosystem services valuation was funded by University Grants Commission, Government of India through UGC Junior

Research Fellowship and his PhD work was nominated as a significant work from the Division of Environment Science, ICAR-Indian Agricultural Research Institute, India. He is specialised in carbon sequestration, ecosystem services, agroecology, climate smart agriculture, farming systems, sustainable agriculture, crop simulation modelling, GHG emissions, agrobiodiversity, bioremediation, economic ornithology, waste recycling and pollution control; He attended and presented his research work in many national and international conferences and also received 'Best oral paper presentation award' and 'Best M.Sc. Thesis award' and 'Young researcher award for excellence in research'. Furthermore, he published more than 24 peer-reviewed publications, 7 book chapters and 70 popular scientific articles in various national and international journals and magazines with 120 citations, h-index is 7, cumulative impact factor is 30. He is also involved in translating many technical documents, including the Environmental Impact Assessment Draft by the Government of India. He is nominated as a Subject Expert Member in Book Selection Committee for Public Libraries under Government of Tamil Nadu since June 2024 and expert member in various organisations including Food and Agricultural Organization, Rome. He has work experience as a Journalist and Editorial member in a top magazine. His aim is to bridge the science and society to uplift the downtrodden people by breaking the stereotypical norms and customs through research and communication. Currently, he is writing and editing books for CRC Press (UK), Nova Science (USA), and Bentham Science publishers (UAE).

Contact: gkdineshiari@gmail.com; dineshg1@srmist.edu.in